

BRAZIL COVID19 data and forecast of total infections and deaths, June 14th, 2020

● Total actually positive cases

● Total deaths

● Verhulst forecast of deaths

● Verhulst forecast of total actually positive cases

BRAZIL COVID19 data of new infections and deaths,
June 14th, 2020

